

**Landholders' Perceptions
of Farm Forestry in the
Northern Rivers Region
of New South Wales**

overview report

by

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. PREAMBLE	1
2. BACKGROUND	1
2.1 Farm forestry in the Northern Rivers region of New South Wales	1
2.2 The rural community in the Northern Rivers region of New South Wales	4
2.3 Theories to guide interpretation of attitudinal data:	5
2.4 Groups formed through the use of hierarchical cluster analysis	10
3. METHODS	12
4. RESULTS	14
4.1 The 'innovators' perspective	14
4.2 The 'progressive' perspective	15
4.3 The 'lifestyler' perspective	16
4.4 The 'middle-of-the-road' perspective	17
4.5 The 'traditional' perspective	20
5. DISCUSSION	22
5.1 General issues raised by landholders	22
5.2 The relevance of group classification using innovation adoption theory	24
5.3 The importance of perceptions about farm forestry across the region	25
6. CONCLUSIONS	27
7. REFERENCES	31

FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1: Factors influencing the decisions to plant trees for timber production on private lands.	3
Figure 2: Factors determining a person's behaviour (Source: Ajzen and Fishbein 1980, p.8)	6
Table 1: Stages in the innovation adoption process (Rogers 1995)	7
Figure 3: The S-curve of the adoption of new practices over time (from Rogers 1995).	8
Table 2: Characteristics of different 'ideal' types of landholders (from Howden <i>et al.</i> 1998).	9
Table 3: Selected characteristics of groups defined according to reasons for planting and managing trees by the use of cluster analysis (Specht and Emtage 1998).	11
Table 4: Selected socio-economic characteristics and perceptions of groups of landholders, defined according to their reasons for planting and/or managing trees (a to f), and their comparison with types of landholders as defined by Howden <i>et al.</i> (1998), and their characteristics (1 to 3).	12
Table 5: Perceptions and associated socio-economic features characterising extreme positions of landholders' attitudes to farm forestry and land management objectives.	25
Table 6: Perceived Constraints to farm forestry development	29

1. PREAMBLE

This document provides an overview of a project conducted to investigate the perceptions of landholders in the Northern Rivers Region of New South Wales to commercially-oriented farm forestry. This project was undertaken for the Northern Rivers Regional Plantations Committee with funding supplied by the Federal Department of Primary Industries and Energy under the Farm Forestry Program. The project was conducted in two parts.

A questionnaire was used in the first part of the project. The responses to the questionnaire were analysed to assess the relationships between the topic areas listed below, and to identify groups within the community with different reasons for planting and managing trees that could form the basis for developing and targeting publicly funded farm forestry assistance programs. The full report of the results of this part of the project may be found in Specht and Emtage (1998).

Topics covered in the questionnaire survey included:

- (i) the reasons landholders have for planting and managing trees on their land;
- (ii) perceived restrictions to planting and managing trees;
- (iii) the types of incentive or assistance schemes that would be most valuable to aid participation in farm forestry activities;
- (iv) information sources used to assist land management decisions;
- (v) landholders' tree planting behaviour; and
- (vi) selected socio-economic characteristics of landholders and their landholdings.

The second part of the project, reported in this document, consisted of telephone interviews with respondents who volunteered to be contacted further. These interviews were designed to validate the results of the first part of the project, and to extend and further explore the potential of farm forestry and the factors constraining its development in the Northern Rivers region of New South Wales. The utility and relevance of existing theories of rural sociology and decision-making are examined.

An overview of the information and understanding gained in the project is provided, and recommendations for action proposed.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Farm forestry in the Northern Rivers region of New South Wales

Present involvement in farm forestry in the Northern Rivers region of New South Wales

The results of the survey that formed the first part of this project, and the results of other surveys, indicate that planting trees to produce commercial timber is a relatively uncommon practice in the northern rivers region of New South Wales (Emtage 1995, Wilson and Yannick 1995, Emtage and Specht 1996, Specht and Emtage 1998, Emtage and Specht 1998). The responses in the survey were analysed to elucidate differences in the perceptions and socio-economic characteristics of those who were already planting and managing trees to produce commercial timber and those who were not. It was found that those already involved in farm forestry displayed a number of the personal and socio-economic characteristics commonly associated with people who are quick to take up new or innovative practices according to theories about the diffusion of innovations (Spence 1994, Rogers 1995).

Factors found to affect involvement in farm forestry in the northern rivers region of New South Wales

A number of different techniques were used in the analysis of the responses to the questionnaire. Responses were first described using mean ratings on the Likert scales (0 to 5 rankings) which were used to measure the perceptions of landholders on all topics other than those related to planting behaviour (v) and socio-economic characteristics (vi). Factor analysis was then used to identify groups of questions that were answered in a similar manner by respondents. Analysis of variance was used to assess the relationships between these groups of questions, and between the socio-economic characteristics and tree planting behaviour of the respondents. Finally, hierarchical cluster analyses were used to define groups of landholders with significantly different reasons for planting and managing trees on their land. These groups were examined to assess differences in their socio-economic characteristics, perceptions of the other topics examined in the survey, and actual tree planting behaviour (Specht and Emtage 1998).

Significant variation was found in landholders' perceptions of the appropriate roles for trees on private lands. Landholders gave the highest ratings for the use of trees for 'conservation' and personal reasons, followed by the use of trees for 'shelter'. The use of trees for 'timber' production was rated lowest. The variation within the community was described by the definition, using cluster analysis, of groups with different reasons for planting and managing trees. Relationships between the responses to variables in different topics were also examined, such as between different reasons for planting and the usefulness of different information sources.

A number of socio-economic factors were found to affect landholders' perceptions of farm forestry and their ability to engage in farm forestry activities. Some of these factors included the type of land use, the size of the landholding, the degree of dependence on the landholding for income, and membership of groups associated with land management (Specht and Emtage 1998, Emtage and Specht 1998).

A model of the factors affecting the adoption of farm forestry at the time of the survey was developed. The model was based on analyses of the differences between those persons involved and those not involved in farm forestry for timber production, and the analyses of relationships between topics (Figure 1). It was concluded that while there is some 'cultural' resistance to the adoption of farm forestry in the region, the results clearly illustrated the importance of economic and 'structural' impediments to the development of farm forestry.

The model shown in Figure 1 illustrates the socio-economic factors whose combined effects can result in landholders establishing farm forestry plots for timber production. It can be inferred from this figure that the long time taken for returns from timber plantings has a number of important effects on the ability and willingness of landholders to participate in farm forestry activities. Many of those currently growing trees for timber are: younger than the average age for landholders, have a family which may benefit in the future from the plantings, and derive a significant proportion of their income from off-farm sources. In addition, landholders participating in farm forestry reported a greater than average interest in conservation issues and practices. This translates into a personal interest in trees, and an earlier return of benefits to landholders, as the conservation benefits of farm forestry accrue to landholders much earlier than timber returns (Harrison *et al.* 1998).

Figure 1: Factors influencing the decisions to plant trees for timber production on private lands (Specht and Emtage 1998).

There are other pathways or sets of circumstances that may lead to landholders establishing trees for timber production on their lands. For instance, while age was found to be negatively related to planting trees for timber production, some older people were found to be establishing trees for timber production in partnership with NSW State Forests Joint Venture program in order to reduce the workload of managing their properties.

Ratings of restrictions to tree planting and the usefulness of different potential assistance/incentive schemes also indicated the importance of economic and political factors in determining tree planting and management behaviour. The relative importance of different types of restrictions and incentives was strongly related to the reasons landholders had for planting. Those who had planted for ‘conservation’ reasons only were restricted by the costs of establishing and managing their plantings, but not worried about ‘harvest security’ or ‘prices for wood products’. Landholders whose main reasons for planting were for ‘shelter’ or ‘timber’ were restricted by the money and time needed for planting and managing trees, were concerned about the financial and legal implications of plantation development, and many were not interested in working with outside agencies. It appeared that those who had been planting trees predominantly for ‘shelter’ reasons thought that they already had sufficient tree cover to suit their purpose, and any further tree planting would depend upon the clarification of harvest security and other regulations covering land management.

Responses to the questionnaire indicated that those persons already involved with plantations were as concerned with harvest security and other forms of ‘economic assistance’ as those not involved. Landholders already involved in planting could also see risks involved with plantation development, but were better able to cope with these risks. This could be partly due to factors such as personality, ability to gather and use information, together with financial position and family situation. This supports theories emphasising the effects of individual risk management strategies on management practices (Rogers 1995).

The results of the survey emphasise the importance of information in reducing both production risks and the perception of sovereign risk. Those who had already planted or managed trees for timber production were significantly more ready to use ‘outside’ information sources in guiding their land management decisions than those who had not planted timber. Those who have already planted for timber are more likely to be involved in

groups associated with land management. Another possible reason for some landholders being better able to cope with risk is their greater understanding of the issue through being better informed.

2.2 The rural community in the Northern Rivers region of New South Wales

It is important to understand the sociological characteristics of the region in order to understand why various perceptions have arisen. Rural communities in Australia generally, and particularly those east of the Great Dividing Range, have undergone considerable change in their social and economic structure over the past thirty years (Powys *et al.* 1981, Buggie 1987). This has been due to structural adjustments in agriculture, such as the decline in the number of dairying operations, the increase in beef producers and orchardists, the declining prevalence of the 'family farm', the increased reliance of landholders on off-farm sources of income, the increasing number of rural residential landholdings, and the related influx of 'new settlers' from large urban areas (KRAU 1977, Powys *et al.* 1981). Similar patterns of migration have also been found in the USA, and studies both here and there have found that these people are attracted to rural areas by the ideal of pursuing a more 'wholesome' life in a cleaner environment that is free from both pollution and negative social influences on their children.

Most rural communities have long had the reputation of being tightly-knit, and relatively socially homogeneous and conservative in relation to urban communities. This is no longer true, particularly in regions close to the coast and to large urban centres. Parts of the Northern Rivers region have experienced the highest levels of population growth in Australia over the last twenty years due to immigration from the large urban centres of south-east Australia. These immigrants frequently have different attitudes to farming practices and the 'legitimate' functions of rural lands, and a different level of dependence on their land for income. The change in the composition of the rural community together with the rapid expansion of urban areas in the region has affected community relationships and attitudes to land management issues.

A study of conflicts between 'old' and 'new' settlers in the Bellingen area by Powys *et al.* (1981) concluded that conflict between these groups arose due to disputes over the use of resources rather than because of differences in the belief systems of the groups (see also Taifel and Turner 1986). They found that it was not until the 'new' settlers began to oppose logging operations in the Black Scrub area that relations between the two groups soured; the council began to challenge illegal dwellings that had been erected on rural lands, and the 'old' settlers took exception to the way the 'new' settlers were using the local community centre. Very similar processes have been at work in the study area since the Aquarius festival in Nimbin in 1973 and the blockading of Terania Creek from 1979 (Gibbs 1992). Landholders have similar concerns about sovereign risks and intra-community disputes in the Wet Tropics area of far north Queensland following changes in the social composition of that region and the declaration of the Wet Tropics World Heritage Area (Harrison *et al.* 1998).

A high level of mistrust of governments was recorded in responses to the questionnaire, and in other recent surveys of landholders in some regions of Australia (Harrison *et al.* 1998). The rapidly changing social and economic environment is frightening to many older rural landholders who feel that they are no longer listened to. They are often not as articulate as the 'new' settlers in the region and are less comfortable or acquainted with political processes.

Major changes to government policies or 'first order' events such as the Rainforest Policy Decision of 1982 (NSW) and the Wet Tropics World Heritage Area declaration (Qld) are not the only events eroding the confidence of landholders and foresters in the future of the forestry industry. 'Second order' events also have major cumulative effects on the lives and livelihoods of those in the forest industry in Australia (Dargavel *et al.* 1995). These are events

which do not 'change the policies, structures or processes at the national or State level in any significant way, but which still have noticeable social and environmental effects' (Dargavel *et al.* 1995, p.225). Disputes over the management of public forests have been concerned with which areas should be managed as State Forests and which as National Parks, where road construction and logging activities should be allowed, and how such operations should be carried out (Dargavel *et al.* 1995). Second order events have a cumulative effect on the forestry industry. In combination with first order events and experienced over a long time they 'have slowly eroded the bases on which ... small [logging] firms survive, the belief systems of the individuals, their family traditions, and the sense that they have a future in the industry' (Dargavel *et al.* 1995, p.228). Many people involved in the timber industry are members of the wider rural community in the northern rivers region. Landholders know them socially, and look to them for advice on forestry matters.

2.3 Theories to guide interpretation of attitudinal data:

social psychology, innovation adoption, market segmentation and rural sub-cultures

The analysis of the responses to the survey indicated that there is considerable diversity in the attitudes to farm forestry in the region. It is appropriate and necessary for landholders to be considered as individuals by extension officers seeking to encourage farm forestry. Advice to each landholder needs to be tailored to suit their financial situation, land-use type, goals for land management, and their forestry skills, as outlined by Raintree (1987) and Stewart and Reid (1994).

Considering each landholder as an individual creates difficulties, however, for the development of policies and programs by public agencies seeking to encourage farm forestry. Comparison between individuals is required to gauge the range of opinions in the community, and groups of individuals with similar opinions can be used economically as targets for development programs (Chamala 1987, Byron and Boutland 1987, Emtage 1995, Emtage and Specht 1996, Emtage and Specht 1998, Vanclay *et al.* 1998). The use of simple analyses like gross averages or case studies ignores the scope for improving participation in commercial farm forestry for timber production through the use of theories relating to the diffusion of innovations (Rogers 1995, and Spence 1994), social psychology and social network analysis (Ajzen and Fishbein 1980, Scott 1991), market segmentation (Boyd *et al.* 1989, Dillon *et al.* 1990), and rural sub-cultures (Vanclay *et al.* 1998). All of the above theoretical approaches are linked by a common background—the theories of social psychology. These theories attempt to describe and explain the ways in which people make decisions and relate to each other. A brief overview of some of the relevant parts of these theories is presented below.

Social psychology and the theory of reasoned action

Belief systems, norms, communication behaviour, sub-cultures, attitudes and behaviour.

The theory of reasoned action describes the factors that have been found to influence decision making by individuals (Ajzen and Fishbein 1980). The theory holds that the behaviour of most people in most situations is not driven by sub-conscious needs or cravings, but rather is the result of a reasoned appraisal of the likely positive and negative consequences of an action (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Factors determining a person's behaviour (Source: Ajzen and Fishbein 1980, p.8)

It is thought that an appraisal of these consequences is based on information from two types of sources: (i) what an individual thinks will be the outcome of the behaviour, based on their previous experiences, and (ii) the opinions of 'significant others' about the likely outcomes. The relative importance placed to the appraisal of each of these sources varies between individuals and according to different circumstances.

Researchers in the discipline of social psychology have found that while everyone is an individual, and their attitudes to the world are shaped by their individual experiences, people are also naturally gregarious. Thus they tend to form sub-cultures and, at a smaller scale, cliques, consisting of groups of people who have similar sets of values and norms, and therefore similar attitudes and behavioural responses to stimuli (Ajzen and Fishbein 1980, Scott 1991). These sub-cultures can thus form a basis for defining and describing the variation of attitudes toward farm forestry in the rural community in a way that can be used to develop programs and strategies to promote farm forestry to a diverse community.

Innovation adoption

The theories describing the diffusion of innovations have been used as the basis for extension practices in Australia for the last three decades. These theories apply many of the concepts developed by social psychologists in an attempt to explain the process by which new ideas become known in a community and new practices are adopted (Rogers 1995). It is thought that there are a number of different types of people in a community in terms of the way they respond to new ideas and practices. There are a number of factors which influence decisions to adopt new practices, and the process occurs over a number of stages (Table 1).

Table 1: Stages in the innovation adoption process (Rogers 1995)

Stage in the innovation adoption process	Factors affecting stage
Prior conditions	Previous practice Felt needs/problems Innovativeness
I. Knowledge of the innovation	Norms of the social system Socio-economic characteristics Personality variables
II. Persuasion to adopt	Communication behaviour Relative advantage Compatibility Complexity Triability
III. Decision to adopt	Observability
IV. Implementation	Above factors
V. Confirmation	Considerations of the effects of the innovation

The theories of innovation adoption and social psychology describe the tendencies for people to communicate with others who share and reinforce their own world views (Rogers 1995, Spence 1994, Scott 1991). Theories of innovation adoption go further to describe a common process whereby new ideas are spread through the community (Figure 3). New ideas and practices are initiated and trialed first by the 'innovators', then they spread to 'early adopters' and 'opinion leaders', and finally to the 'early' and 'late' majorities (Spence 1994, Rogers 1995).

Although extension sciences have been criticised for treating the rural community as a homogenous entity, through the use of innovation adoption theories they have 'in some ways invoked diversity on the basis of innovativeness' (Vanclay *et al.* 1998, p.85). This application of innovation adoption theories has not been sufficient as 'this was not a true form of diversity because extension, at least in traditional models, presumed that innovations were universally applicable and would be universally adopted' (Vanclay *et al.* 1998, p.85, also see Vanclay and Lawrence 1995).

Some of the criticism made by Vanclay and Lawrence (1995) of the use of innovation diffusion theories by extension services arises where the theories have been used as an excuse to decrease overall extension budgets by concentrating extension efforts on the 'early adopters' and 'opinion leaders' in the belief that the messages would eventually trickle down to other landholders. This would seem, however, to be a criticism of the way in which these theories are applied rather than of the theories themselves. Another criticism of the innovation adoption approach that is perhaps more relevant is that it fails to recognise the diversity of belief systems in communities. Instead, differences in behaviour are explained as resulting from different perceptions of risk and different socio-economic circumstances.

Figure 3: The S-curve of the adoption of new practices over time (from Rogers 1995).

Any group within the rural community may contain a range of different types of people described by innovation adoption theories. Spence (1992), points out that different groups can be defined as more or less 'innovative' themselves, in that different groups will condone or tolerate different degrees of adoption of innovative practices by its members before ostracising them.

Market segmentation analysis

Previous research has identified the potential for the use of some of the techniques employed by market segment research to assist those designing and administering rural development programs (Chamala 1987, Vanclay *et al.* 1998), although very little has been published about the approach (Emtage 1995, Emtage and Specht 1996). Market segmentation is an analysis technique used by commercial firms to guide their marketing strategies and resource allocation between products and markets (Dillon *et al.* 1990). In this sense, market segments are sub-groups of consumers who respond to a given marketing strategy in a similar manner, or who exhibit differing sensitivities to some marketing-mix element. Market segmentation can be used, for example, to assess how different types of people will respond to new packaging or advertising, or to a new product. It is suggested that market segmentation is a necessary part of any effective marketing strategy, as products cannot be correctly 'positioned' in a market, or targeted to certain consumers, if the reactions of different parts of the market to different products and marketing strategies is unknown (Dillon *et al.* 1990).

Market segmentation methods were adopted for this study of landholders' attitudes to tree planting and management on their land. The perceived benefits of the different uses for trees on private lands were used as the basis for clustering respondents. Analysis of variance and chi-square tests were then used to describe the tree-planting attitudes and the socio-economic characteristics of each group.

Rural sub-cultures and farming styles

Vanclay and other researchers based at the Centre for Rural Research (at Charles Sturt University in Wagga Wagga) have been trying to develop methodologies appropriate for studying the effects of rural sub-cultures on private land management because 'extension, in particular, has failed to appreciate the significance of sociocultural diversity in developing its extension programs and in the targeting of its messages' (Vanclay *et al.* 1998, p.85). Like Chamala (1987), Vanclay points out that the techniques of market researchers, who use market segmentation as the basis for developing and selling products, has a lot to teach those developing rural extension services. While the producers and sellers of agricultural equipment and other products appear to have a great deal of information about the different types of landholders, the information is commercially sensitive and therefore unpublished (Vanclay *et al.* 1998). This means that Australian researchers concerned with the effective delivery of rural extension services will have to develop their own methodologies and databases that are accessible to the public.

The Centre for Rural Social Research at Charles Sturt University has undertaken a number of studies using the idea of rural sub-cultures (Vanclay 1992, Vanclay and Lawrence 1995), and the ideas of 'styles of farming' adapted from ideas developed by Dutch extension theorists (Vanclay *et al.* 1998, Howden *et al.* 1998). The studies based on the 'styles of farming' methodology have attempted to derive categories or groups of landholders from descriptions by the landholders themselves and analysis by researchers, agronomists and extension agents. These studies produced up to 27 different categories of landholders, although the main six categories are thought to account for 80% of all types of landholders (Howden *et al.* 1998). It was indicated that the researchers saw the categories as ideals or archetypes rather than being distinct entities. The characteristics of the main groups are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Characteristics of different 'ideal' types of landholders (from Howden *et al.* 1998).

Category	Degree of contact with researchers/ change agents	Level of risk adopted	Key influences	Views of other landholders
Innovative	High - used to trial new practices	High - like to try new ideas	Look to the 'big picture'	Forefront of change, take some unnecessary risks.
Progressive	High	Medium - trial 'proven' practices	Strong economic/business orientation	Seen by many as the 'best' farmers.
Middle of the road	Medium	Medium - low	Other landholders. Like the farming 'way-of-life', have inherited land.	Seen as 'average', follow-on' or 'practical' farmers.
Lifestyler	Medium-low	High - low	Personal approaches; some new to land, others are retired farmers.	Adopt 'strange' management. Annoying if they challenge neighbours practices or fail to control weeds.
Resource limited-structural	Medium - low	Low	Small and often unviable farm size. Low financial and information capital limits practices.	Some lack of business skills and ability to cope with new information.
Traditional	Low	Low	Follow well-known practices, often those of their parents.	Seen as 'old-fashioned', living in the past.

Howden *et al.* (1998) and Vanclay *et al.* (1998) concluded that the categorisation of farmers according to their farming styles was a useful technique for improving the design and delivery of rural extension services. The definition of 27 categories does cause some problems for those planning and administering public development and extension services because it is unlikely that 27 individual types of schemes could be efficiently run. This level of detail would be useful to on-ground extension personnel, however, and public administrators could concentrate on targeting the main groups identified.

Phillips and Gray (1995) have looked to another European theoretical base to describe the variation in farming styles and differential rate of adoption of innovative practices within the Australian rural community. They argue that the concentration on economic variables to differentiate sectors within the community ignores important social and cultural influences on farming practices. They cited a number of studies from New Zealand, Canada, the USA and France which have concluded that landholders choose their land management practices guided by their desire to have good standing in the community as a 'good farmer' and citizen more than to maximise their profits. They argue that 'it would appear that the criterion of respectability and participation and, most importantly, are far more appropriate ranking mechanisms as used by farmers themselves' (Phillips and Gray 1995, p.130).

In this way they support the work of French social theorist Bourdieu who has developed the approach of generative structuralism. This approach seeks to explain the behaviour of farmers in terms of the interaction of 'social fields' which appear to be similar to social networks. In these social fields relative positions of influence and authority are accorded to those with symbolic, cultural and economic capital. There are some departures from the theories of reasoned action with the idea of 'habitus'. This idea refers to the person's world-view or picture of reality which is used 'without self-conscious calculation or discursive articulation' to provide strategy to decision-making (Phillips and Gray 1995, p.129).

Phillips and Gray discuss the results of qualitative studies of farmers and their families in the Riverina region. They state that there was a diversity of opinions about what constituted 'good farming practices'. It is concluded that 'according to how the social field and habitus of an individual farmer constructs the notion of 'good' farming, the farmer may or may not find the adoption of sustainable [or farm forestry] practices, however defined, appropriate and desirable' (Phillips and Gray 1995, p.131).

2.4 Groups formed through the use of hierarchical cluster analysis

In the first part of this project, groups within the farming community were defined and described by analysing responses to a written survey. In this way it was intended that groups of landholders with similar reasons for planting and managing trees could be defined who could form the basis for the development of farm forestry programs in the Northern Rivers region (Specht and Emtage 1998, Emtage and Specht 1998). Cluster analysis of the respondents resulted in the formation of five groups with significantly different reasons for planting and managing trees. Some 27% of the respondents were not included in any group. The socio-economic characteristics and responses of these groups to the topics in the questionnaire were then assessed using analysis of variance to determine what characterised them (apart from their different reasons for planting and managing trees) and whether the groups were sociologically unique.

The groups were characterised socio-economically according to the actual and relative size of landholding, the number of years the land had been owned, the proportion of land covered by native vegetation, and the types of land uses practised. Significant differences between the groups were found for the socio-economic variables 'land size' ($p < 0.001$), 'activity type' ($p < 0.05$), 'mean land size' ($p < 0.10$), the 'number of groups' belonged to ($p < 0.15$), and the number of 'years owned' ($p < 0.10$). Significant differences between the groups were found for the behavioural variables 'percent cover of native vegetation' ($p < 0.10$), if planted 'more than twenty trees' ($p < 0.05$), if planted for 'timber' ($p < 0.05$), if planted for 'beautification' ($p < 0.10$), and if planted for 'soil protection' ($p < 0.10$). Significant differences between the groups were found for ratings on the scales 'government information', 'conservation information' (which included the use of abstract information, such as books), 'economic assistance' and 'others assistance' (all with $p < 0.01$) (Specht and Emtage 1998). Selected data about the groups are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Selected characteristics of groups defined according to reasons for planting and managing trees by the use of cluster analysis (Specht and Emtage 1998).

Group number	planted > 20 trees (%)	planted 'timber' (%)	rural residential (%)	log mean land size (ha)	Native vegetation cover (% total land area)	activity type	average no. years education	average no. years land owned
1	75	8	25	1.61	37	Mixed	14.5	14.4
2	85	63	28	1.73	47	Grazing/ cropping	13.5	15.2
3	96	80	41	1.60	42	Rural residential /mixed	14.6	15.7
4	72	14	53	1.37	22	Grazing	15.1	10.9
5	52	5	18	2.34	39	Grazing	13.3	26.5

These groups can be compared with those defined by Howden *et al.* (1998), using modified innovation adoption theory as illustrated in Table 2. By comparing the attributes of each group, Group 1 can be considered comparable to 'middle-of-the-road', Group 2, as 'innovative', Group 3 as 'progressive', Group 4 as 'lifestyler' and Group 5 as 'traditional' (Table 4). There were significant differences between the groups in terms of their perception of the importance of different information sources and the usefulness of different types of potential farm forestry assistance schemes. The 'progressives' and 'innovators' rated conservation information sources significantly higher than the later adoptees, and were more ready to accept assistance from others than the more traditional landholders. Group membership was significantly higher for the 'innovators' and 'progressives' than for the other groups with the exception of the 'traditionalists' whose group membership, although not as high, was higher than for other groups. This suggests that different types of landholders should be contacted through different communication channels, and that a variety of programs will be required to stimulate the development of farm forestry in different sectors of the community. The dependence of the landholders on their land for income (and hence the degree of risk they may be assumed to be able to take) is highest for the 'traditionalists' and lowest for the 'progressives'.

Table 4: Selected socio-economic characteristics and perceptions of groups of landholders, defined according to their reasons for planting and/or managing trees (a to f), and their comparison with types of landholders as defined by Howden *et al.* (1998), and their characteristics (1 to 3).

Groups according to Specht and Emtage (1998)	Categories according to Howden <i>et al.</i> (1998)	1. Degree of contact with researchers / change agents		2. Level of risk adopted		3. Key influences	
		a. Nos of groups belonged to	b. <i>Others assistance</i> (out of five)	c. Average income from land (%)	d. Already planted for timber (%)	e. <i>Conser-vation info.</i> (out of five)	f. <i>Govern-ment info.</i> (out of five)
2	Innovative	19	3.0	30	63	3.6	2.9
3	Progressive	15	2.8	18	80	3.4	2.3
4	Lifestyler	10	2.9	34	14	2.9	2.2
1	Middle of the road	9	2.2	37	8	2.7	2.2
5	Traditional	11	2.2	51	5	2.2	1.9

3. METHODS

This component of the project used telephone interviews to determine landholders' perceptions of farm forestry. It was designed:

- to confirm and validate the findings of the analysis of responses to the questionnaire survey;
- to investigate specific issues identified from the analysis of responses to the questionnaire survey;
- to investigate issues not fully covered in the questionnaire survey; and
- to assess the relevance of the classification of landholders proposed by Howden *et al.* (1998) to the sample surveyed in the Northern Rivers region.

An important role of the telephone interviews was to obtain information about landholders' perceptions of farm forestry in their own words. The analysis of responses to the questionnaire improved our understanding of the relationships between factors affecting farm forestry development by describing and quantifying the nature of relationships between information sources, the type of land use practiced, off-farm income, age, education, the reasons for and restrictions to planting, and types of assistance wanted. Understanding these relationships is vital for developing, targeting and prioritising farm forestry programs because it provides an understanding of the relative influence of economic and physical restrictions to farm forestry. The responses to the questionnaire did not fully articulate the overall perspective which landholders have of farm forestry. Missing was the landholder's perception of the legitimate place of farm forestry in their vision of 'proper' land management. The questionnaire effectively measured the attitudes of individual landholders to some farm forestry issues, but it did not enquire about the attitudes of other landholders known to respondents and therefore did not gain an understanding of the messages being communicated within social networks.

The telephone survey of landholders was designed to meet the aims listed above. All calls were made by one of the authors. Each call was taped (with permission from the interviewee) and typed into a text file on a personal computer.

Description of the sample and sampling method

The sample of landholders contacted for the telephone interviews was drawn from landholders who had responded to the questionnaire and had indicated on the questionnaire form a willingness to participate in further discussions about the topic. Approximately half of the respondents did so.

Five respondents from each cluster group were interviewed (including the ungrouped respondents). Within each group, landholders of relatively young age with relatively large holdings were targeted, although these were not the only types sampled. A total of 26 interviews were conducted.

Interview procedure

The telephone interviews were semi-structured. Calls to landholders were made in September and October 1998, mostly between the hours 9am until 6pm, with some concentration on the period 12 noon to 2pm in an attempt to find landholders home for lunch.

The topics covered in the survey and their associated questions were as follows:

- (i) native forest management (whether timber had been sourced from areas of native vegetation, whether they had sold any timber from these areas, their perception of the financial returns and quality of work undertaken, whether they manage their native vegetation for timber production, their intentions with respect to future harvesting);
- (ii) planting for timber (intentions to plant, main restrictions to planting);
- (iii) social network (did they know any other landholders involved in planting for timber, what were these other persons' impressions of the success or otherwise of their plantings, what did others they know think of planting for timber);
- (iv) public assistance (did they think that there was sufficient assistance available from public agencies to assist farm forestry development); and,
- (v) assistance wanted (what type(s) of assistance would be of greatest use, what form(s) should it take).

Data analysis

The data obtained from the interviews were analysed according to the listed aims of this section of the project. The 'Scenario'¹ program was used to assist the organisation and analysis of the transcripts. This program allows users to classify words, phrases and/or whole transcripts according to who is speaking, the topic referred to, and the feeling associated with that response. Each respondent was identified in the file by the identification code that was used for entering and analysing the responses to the questionnaire so that the data could be linked if necessary. Reports were generated according to the aims, such as 'all comments about public assistance', or 'all positive comments about general restrictions to planting timber by members of group 5'.

¹ Scenario: A computer program for qualitative research from R&D Integral Research.

4. RESULTS

The following sections describe in detail the perceptions of farm forestry held by the different types of landholders identified in the region according to the groups defined using responses to the questionnaires and the telephone interviews. The groups are named as follows:

- (i) Innovators (Group 2);
- (ii) Progressives (Group 3);
- (iii) Lifestylers (Group 4);
- (iv) Middle-of-the-roaders (Group 1); and
- (v) Traditionalists (Group 5).

4.1 The 'innovators' perspective

Innovators are typically people who like to experiment with new ideas and practices. Because they do not like to follow prescriptive management strategies and like to try many different types of enterprises they could be viewed as 'alternatives' by other sectors of the community in the Northern Rivers region. As one landholder said 'I muck around doing a lot of things'. Some of the enterprises being tried by members of this group at present include aquaculture, and oil and bushfoods production from native species of trees and shrubs. They are generally well educated, with moderate reliance on off-farm income, but they always have some enterprise running on their land. They are frequently involved with groups associated with land management.

This group is best represented by some of the members of Groups 2 (innovative) and 3 (progressive) from the first part of the project (Tables 3 and 4). These groups gave the highest ratings of importance to every function for trees on their lands and every type of information source. They still rated the conservation functions of trees as the most important. Many comments would indicate that personal rather than commercial reasons are their primary motivation for attempting to grow timber.

Q: *So you're definitely not into the monocultural idea?*

A: *No.*

Q: *You've got more personal interest in growing mixed species?*

A: *Yeah.*

Maybe I'd like to be able to use some of the timber, or maybe barter it or sell it or something, but I don't know. I might not want to chop it down.

...after a little while I'll cut out some of the poorer quality eucalyptus, and just leave that silky oak-eucalyptus alliance in there as a woodlot. That's the plan. I'll probably be dead before it comes to fruition but that doesn't matter.

Information about tree growing is not restrictive for these landholders as they happily interact with government departments and other sources of research data. They are more restricted by the physical and economic difficulties associated with tree establishment such as getting quality stock and controlling rabbits and wallabies.

Q: *Mostly it's physical problems rather than ...your finding a lack of information?*

A: *Oh no, I've got quite a solid base of information together, no that's okay. It's just getting up and doing it. Yeah, and when you are looking at such a long term project too, you know, it's not really an immediate bread and butter issue.*

As described by Spence (1994), there are differences in the degree of innovativeness tolerated by different social groups. It appears that landholders who subscribe to 'alternative' philosophies about land management are more open to new ideas and practices than those whose views are more 'traditional', as would be expected, given that the 'alternative'

movement is relatively new in the area, and still sorting out its own definitions of 'best management practices'.

A: *The government couldn't show you one stand of red cedar or blue fig or anything they've planted.*

Q: *No, well up around here...in Lismore, there's a few demonstrations on, so they've put in the big species in the timber plantations.*

A: *It would be half an acre here, an acre or two there.*

Q: *Yeah it's all very early in the piece.*

A: *All the hippies have gone into it. That's who they learn it off.*

One of the major differences between members of the 'innovators' group and the other groups is that many seem to personally know other landholders who are experimenting with timber plantations, particularly with ways of combining timber production with biodiversity conservation and bushfood production.

4.2 The 'progressive' perspective

Progressive landholders are described by Howden *et al.* (1998) as being perceived as the 'best farmers', what innovation adoption theorists would term the 'opinion leaders' in a community. They have large or relatively large landholdings for their area, a strong commercial orientation and are easily able to understand and adapt information from abstract sources.

Many landholders in the Woodenbong/Grevillia/Bonalbo area reported that they have been approached by different organisations who wish to establish joint venture plantations on their land. Results from the questionnaire indicated that the landholders with the largest holdings in the western districts of the region were significantly more likely to be involved with joint venture partners. This is probably because they have a sufficient area of land maintain their other activities and see timber plantations as a chance to diversify their income. This attitude is illustrated in the following comments.

Yeah I know [my brother's] a bit against it, but I had a bank manager a long time ago who said you should have your eggs in different baskets, so I just thought, well, that's why I started going into corn, and then went into this.

I do know that when he sat down and worked out the amount of cattle he can run on it plus the price and so on and so forth [he found] that we was breaking even. He sort of said well I'm not really having to have the financial outlay on the cattle, we can still run the same amount of cattle on the rest of the place without actually that block. So that was sort of what we decided on, we just hope it works that's all. That's the only thing that we are concerned about, but I mean it's a gamble like everything else so it doesn't really matter much. You know, but that was sort of basically what we decided to do.

For other landholders in the Tweed, who are on average the oldest in the region, joint venture type arrangements offer them the chance to reduce the workload on their property while still getting some income, as illustrated by these comments.

I suppose everyone has their own reason for doing it, and I suppose I'd better tell you my reason. Old age, and I couldn't look after the whole farm, so I've reduced my herd, and what I liked about it was that you could do, or have as much involvement with the forest as you wanted, and I chose just to maintain the fire-breaks, and they do all the poisoning and all that sort of stuff...so, no, I've been very happy with them. Well, it's cut my work in half, I don't have to poison up the back, so...I've got 20 ha, 50 acres [under trees?] yeah..., I'm very happy with it.

Q: *I see, so you'd be looking to another way to earn money?*

A: *Yes, yes, and so we won't have so much work with the beef cattle.*

Well as a matter of fact the gross of the trees is probably equal to the gross of the cattle, but with the trees there's no expense to come out except the rates, where you've got drenching work, feed and weaning, and all the work with the cattle, which probably brings their gross back to about half way. You get what I mean.

4.3 The 'lifestyler' perspective

There were a number of landholders whose primary land management aim was revegetation of the great majority of their holding for reasons such as biodiversity, conservation, aesthetics, and protection of waterways. Conservation objectives for this group are generally paramount, but they do not exclude the use of trees for timber under a sustained management system except in the most extreme cases.

Q: *So you're not too concerned about harvesting them?*

A: *Um, I'm sort of saying it will be a twenty five to forty year span so it would put me well into my retirement.*

A: *Oh well, I know quite a few people who are doing it, just because I'm involved in the farm forestry. I get the newsletter so I meet up with people like that. Um, locally I don't really know, no not anyone. They're doing a lot of regen. work and planting trees but they're sort of half hearted about whether or not they're going to fell them. I mean that's not an issue at the moment.*

A: *I think it's important to look at the entire ecosystem and the longevity of it, rather than just a quick fix, or quick dollars and cents thing.*

Some interviewees in this group expressed concern about other values of the forest.

Q: *I see you've got a bit of native forest which you're not interested in using for timber?*

A: *No, there's platypus found in there...there's a river down there.*

Q: *...so your main goal is to regenerate the natural forest is it?*

A: *Yeah, yeah. Well it's a gully and it's about a kilometre away. There's a primary conservation area, Emerys Scrub, and I mean it would be nice to sort of connect it all up.*

A: *...well maybe I'd like to at least be able to use some of the timber or maybe barter it or sell it or something, but I don't know; I might not want to chop it down later.*

Q: *You're just happy to grow the trees anyway?*

A: *Well, yes.*

This group thought that trees have an important role to play in providing environmental benefits to the landholder and society at large, not unlike the 'traditionals'. The difference was that their definition of the type of land that needed 'protection' under trees was far broader than that used by the 'traditionals', and they appeared to be quite willing to dedicate substantial proportions of their land to tree growing even with no prospect of financial returns. Their vision of what constitutes legitimate use of rural land can be quite different to that of the 'traditional' commercially-oriented landholders.

The typical landholders in this group were interested in 'farming' only the mostly highly productive parts of their holdings (i.e. those with fertile soils, very gentle slope, and close to their dwellings). Most derive the majority of their income from off-farm occupations or investments. Some had small orchards of traditional crops such as stonefruits; some had plantings of native fruit or oil producing species; and many were committed to organic farming methods. A number of these landholders expressed the desire for information about chemical-free vegetation management options.

A lot of information seems old, very old fashioned, you know. Very chemically based. You have to do this, you have to do that. This much for so many weeks and this much for six months and then you have to dip them in this, you know, after you've picked them...So yeah. There's not very much information, good information, for small scale stuff, I don't think.

Q: And how do you find the public agency support, has it been useful?

A: To a degree. It's more for main stream farming and so forth. Other member groups cost money to join each year, so yeah, there's a financial burden there again I guess.

These landholders were concentrated in the Brunswick and Wilsons River catchments, although pockets of similar landholders are located around Tabulam, Legume, Drake and Nymboida in the Upper Clarence river catchment, and around Grafton.

The costs of establishing and managing trees are the most important factors restricting many of the 'lifestyle' landholders as one interviewee from this group commented.

But I'm sure more land holders would be into planting a lot more of the trees, but it does take time and energy and finances to plant them with success, and I think if anything that's what is holding people back.

4.4 The 'middle-of-the-road' perspective

The 'middle-of-the-road' perspective is relevant to many of the medium sized landholdings in the region. These landholdings appear to be only just large enough to be viable, and many of these landholders have been hit hard by the reduced returns from grazing. These landholders have a strong belief in farming as a way of life, and have many beliefs in common with the 'traditional' perspective.

The perception of the 'proper' function for timber plantings and native vegetation in the 'traditional' rural sub-culture is that they are appropriate on the 'poorer' or less productive areas of the region generally, and on individual landholdings, to provide stock shelter and additional income from timber, as well as farm beautification, and consequent improvement of land values, and some environmental benefits (e.g. soil/land protection, stream/river bank protection, wildlife habitat etc.). These 'poorer' areas include the steeper slopes and less fertile soils on individual landholdings.

Q: ...so you just don't think that the financial returns are good enough?

A: No, and they, the forestry for Joint Ventures, only want your good, clear land, they don't want your steeper land.

A: Well they're planting on some of the good soil around Mallanganee, what's called good country. And good country for beef is apparently good country for trees. But there's a problem there and the problem is that a lot of this second grade country is long term tree country; it takes a long time to grow it, and it seems ridiculous to take it back to scratch to start a plantation.

A: But I can see what they're doing in the outlying areas. They're buying up big farms and planting all the eucalyptus and stuff, but I think it's going to kill the area for fifteen or twenty years. There's going to be no people there, there's no one living there, [the] school will close, shops close, everything else will close. I reckon it's crazy. There's plenty of land that is not really suitable for farming and that sort of thing, you can plant trees on.

Q: I'd suppose they'd argue that that sort of land is not commercially viable for forestry either; they'd find it unsuitable.

A: Yes, well perhaps they should limit the size of their blocks, or something like that, to keep the people in the area somehow, I don't know. That's just the way I see it.

This attitude was prevalent among landholders who used their landholdings to provide a substantial proportion of their income (i.e. households who derive more than about 30% of their income from agricultural activities). This attitude was also common to rural residential landholders who identify themselves with, and hold attitudes similar to those of, the traditional farming community. This includes landholders who are predominantly retired from farming but still keep some stock to 'pay the rates' etc. It also includes some rural residential landholders who are still of working age and gain most of their income from urban occupations. They also commonly run small herds of cattle on their land, often through agistment. Many of these smaller landholders with cattle, particularly in the drier and more remote areas of the region, appear to strongly associate their attitudes with those of the traditional rural culture.

Because of the size of their operations, the challenge to remain financially viable restricts the planting activities of many of the landholders in this group. They need regular income.

I suppose the main problem is the age problem. I'm coming up to sixty four, and anything I planted I wouldn't be able to harvest it. With this carbon credit system, I'd be interested in it. If that comes good.

Most of the farmers that I mix with are just full tilt dairy farmers. The trees that will help the cows and the crops they've planted, they certainly don't see forestry as good a proposition as milking cows.

All I can see that I'll be doing would be losing whatever land that I had for cattle to growing timber, and I couldn't see much benefit ...out of it really...perhaps I can get more [income] out of the bit of land with the timber, but just from my point of view it wouldn't be what I want to do really. I can grow quite a lot of timber without putting any good land into it.

We don't have a big enough area to do that, because we want to run our dairy, our dairy cattle, and there's just not enough property to have trees as well because it certainly ties your land up for a long time, and I can understand that it would be a good idea, but if we tied up a few acres like that, quite a few acres, we would not be able to survive.

I'm using the bulk of my land for cattle. I guess that the long term nature of it [restricts me], and I need cash flow now to survive. It really doesn't matter how much the tree is worth in twenty years time. I've got to put food on the table now. So that's the first problem. I guess the other one is really the uncertainty of what it may be worth in the long term. I can see with my stone fruit a pretty good return, but from planting for timber, to me that's more of a gamble. And at this stage in my life and finances I don't have that luxury.

Q: *What would you see as being the main restrictions to your planting for timber?*

A: *Land area. It's an operational dairy farm with only 240 acres or thereabouts. I sort of can't. I know we could get cattle back into it after a few years, but we sort of can't really justify taking blocks, sufficient areas out for long enough periods...nibbling away bits here and there, we are achieving most of the things we want to do.*

Q: *So it's a matter of maintaining a viable herd size?*

A: *That's right.*

The most commonly cited reasons for not becoming involved in planting or managing trees for timber production by this group of landholders were related to factors associated to the notion of sovereign risk and the related financial risks. Frequent references were made to the notion that the government and/or environmentalists would or could prevent the future harvest of planted trees.

I think the major stumbling block or the main reason people are hesitant is that there doesn't seem to be a guarantee that you'd be able to harvest it. I think that would be the major thing

that I see at the moment. I'm not sure if it's been talked about, if its been resolved or not, I don't think its been totally resolved actually, a guarantee in being able to harvest it. That's probably the main thing, and also selecting species that are suitable for the country.

You know, and as far as timber is concerned, we'd love to put in timber...you know, plant a lot of natives or certain types...We don't know much about what sort of trees but I think native eucalyptus or whatever would probably be the best on our property and we'd like to do that. The only thing is, you know, whether we'd be able, once that's fully grown, to cut them down and sell them.

But I do believe people are generally still concerned about right to harvest. They see the goal posts being shifted frequently, and yeah, I'm sure that's still a major problem.

Not many people are doing it themselves. There's a few farmers that want to do it but there's too many restrictions. If they can't cut them down they're not going to plant them.

Q: *You think that some of the other landholders would be a bit worried about the change in land uses around the place?*

A: *Well I think they think that once the trees are back on it, they're frightened about the green movement I think.*

One of the things about ... I must confess, one of the things about being on a farm and I suppose aggressively independent is that people like myself tend to ignore public bodies wherever possible, and of course it might not be the right thing to do ...

...the greenies won't ever let them build a chipmill or paper mill in Australia anyway.

One way that the perceived incompatibility of forestry with agriculture could be resolved would be to modify the way plantations are set out. This may improve the community's perception of the State Forest Joint Venture scheme, its effects on the rural economy, and effects on individual landholdings.

Q: *The guys, you say, are involved with State Forest. How do you think that's going?*

A: *He's not a dairy farmer. He's got a substantial area of land up on the Clarence, and he's come up with an interesting plan, in that he's dictated to them the nature of the plantings, and they are planted strategically for his livestock, but in sufficient area to satisfy what the Forestry want. In other words they look more like shade, they look more like wildlife corridors, and shade belts and things like that than commercial forestry. Interesting concept the way he's done it. He's achieved the area that they require.*

Q: *And they've been happy to work along with that?*

A: *Well yes....*

The telephone interviews revealed that some people are questioning the products and species choices of NSW State Forests Joint Venture plantings on private lands. In particular, comments were made about the need to grow trees for pulp production when they perceived that the wood left behind from current logging operations is being wasted, and is creating a fire hazard. These people are interested in growing high quality saw and veneer logs.

The fellas growing timber, you know, people who are wanting people to grow timber. I can't really see much point in growing a whole lot of timber for chip wood. I mean, at the present moment they're logging forest and stuff and they're leaving all the heads of trees and all that, and as far as I'm concerned they're just wasting that. And if they were going to grow some

trees for millable logs, which would take a bit longer than thirty years I might add, then I can see the point in that, but I really can't see much point if it's for chips.

Something that would turn out to be a mill log would interest me a lot more. I'd still have to have a look at the thing a bit closer, but yeah it would. It would.

The upper catchments of the Richmond and Clarence Rivers appear to have been targeted by a number of groups seeking to establish plantations in partnership with private landholders. Some respondents report having been approached by three separate agencies. These agencies appear to have researched the returns to grazing in the region and the potential returns from timber production, and are offering landholders contracts which guarantee them income slightly higher than what they have been able to get from other activities.

So yeah, there was somebody from NSW also ringing us about planting trees and so on for harvest. From what I gather there's quite a few people around being approached to grow trees for harvest.

These offers interest some people, but many are maintaining opposition to the development of plantations on the grounds that: forestry is not what they want to do; plantations decrease the flexibility of land management options; plantations are bad for the local economy; and environmentalists will prevent harvest. Some of the stories circulating about the joint-venture schemes will not be helping to improve the acceptance of farm forestry as a legitimate activity for private rural landowners.

A.: There's another property that's planted out near another property of mine, they've planted about 400 hectares maybe even more. I reckon that's a failure too. They actually cleared it in conjunction with the Forestry or whoever it was, but they planted the wrong species. So the country didn't suit the species they planted and they've got more rubbish timber coming up, wattles and all sorts of things coming up, its going to make it pretty hard for the plantation species to get going. Well its going to cost to keep it out, put it that way.

...they're mostly planting white gum, and if you talk to anyone that is in a sawmill, they are not very interested in cutting white gum because it is very hard to dry probably, it will bend and buckle, it dries in patches.

A: Yes, well I take it that the government is going to pay us out when they harvest it. We've got a contract, so I don't see why they shouldn't. But some people, when I've mentioned it to other farmers who haven't got it, they turn and say, oh yeah, but what happens if the government turns around and says they aren't going to pay you? I said well, you've got a contract, and a contract is a contract, it's a legal document.

Q: And what do they say about that?

A: Oh, oh yeah (ha ha)

Q: They're still sceptical?

A: Very very sceptical, yes.

But it's not all bad news for joint venture schemes, as some report that they are very happy with the way things are going.

Yes, well I've been to a couple of get-togethers, meetings for that sort of thing at the golf club, and people who have been doing it have been there, and I haven't heard one person complain about it.

4.5 The 'traditional' perspective

Few of the landholders in this group had planted trees for timber production on their land. Most thought that timber production was not an appropriate use of medium to high quality

rural lands. A number expressed disappointment with the requirements of NSW State Forests Joint Venture for involvement in the scheme. Many wanted to offer their less productive land and were upset that the scheme was not interested in using such lands. There were fears expressed that the practice of State Forests buying out large grazing properties to establish plantations would greatly harm the economies of small rural towns. This practice appeared to offend their ideas of what is appropriate use of agricultural lands. These perceptions are very close to those of the 'middle-of-the-road' perspective.

This attitude was related to the attitude of many that the government regulations regarding land-clearing and or forestry operations on private lands are already too restrictive. Many said they would like to become more involved in farm forestry if they were allowed to clear 'unproductive' species of trees (in relation to their ability to produce quality timber) and replace them with more productive species. Their reason for not doing so was, they stated, the current regulations regarding native forest management.

They conceded that previous land-clearing for agriculture and forestry activities had been environmentally damaging and unsustainable. They claimed, however, that landholders today are very conservation-minded. They feel that the regulators simply do not understand their management strategies and are acting to appease the environmental movement and urban constituencies without proper regard for the 'realities' of life in rural areas.

The concept of 'good land management' for these landholders involves the use of trees to support agricultural activities, as illustrated by the following comment. The comment also indicates the differences in perceptions between what some landholders see as 'real farmers' and 'tree people'.

A: ... because we're at Burringbar where there are a lot of people who are tree people, there are a lot of people growing trees but I wouldn't call them farmers. I would call them tree people who've brought land and they're replanting. We know farmers...most of the farmers we know have been into replanting for a long time. We know people at Bangalow and Byron Bay and places like that who are basically piggery people, and I would think they've been basically planting trees for 20 to 30 years; they've been planting trees for a long time. Mostly for uses that we do: shelter, or wind reduction, that sort of thing...

Q: A bit of soil protection?

A: Oh that, yes, soil protection, that's right. They're sort of good farming practices really. Because most of them bought farms that had been cleared for grazing or banana growing and they were very degraded. I mean, most of our place, it had no topsoil at all when we bought it, dreadful.

I've only got seven hundred acres, so I've got to make a living off seven hundred. If someone had say five or six thousand acres, well then you know I think in some of their country that they shouldn't be cultivating, they probably should think about it. You know, there's some fairly steep hills around here...they could put that back into forestry, if you get what I mean.

And they could create corridors and things like that. I do believe, I'm not a greenie—don't get me wrong there—but I do believe you need trees and things like that. I do think that young trees do a fair bit for the environment, the old trees that they want to save I don't think they put...well I think they've used up their livelihood and they don't put as much...oxygen back in as you think they would.

Few of the landholders in the 'traditional' group know others who are involved in planting trees for timber production.

5. DISCUSSION

A number of issues have been identified which are critical to the future development of farm forestry in the Northern Rivers region. Analysis of the responses to the questionnaire demonstrated the importance of economic factors and showed that there are some 'cultural' factors constraining farm forestry development in the Northern Rivers region. The telephone survey provided information about landholders' perceptions of the broad field of land management, and showed how they think farm forestry can complement their other activities. Some of the perceptions of farm forestry were found to be related to the general question of the management of public and private native forests.

Issues that were identified as constraining farm forestry development included:

- (i) the inability of private landholders to finance large scale tree planting;
- (ii) notions of what are legitimate uses for rural/agricultural lands;
- (iii) confusion about regulations covering native forest management and harvest security;
- (iv) concern about infringement by governments of the 'presumptive entitlements' (Reeve 1994) or 'as of use rights' of landholders;
- (v) concern over the apparent misunderstanding by the wider community of the conservation ethics of landholders; and
- (vi) concern about financial effects of farm forestry on both individual landholdings and on the economies of small rural communities.

5.1 General issues raised by landholders

Role of trees on the land

Responses to the questionnaire and telephone interviews indicated that nearly all landholders felt that trees had an important role to play in providing environmental services on their land and to the wider community. The critical differences between the extreme ends of the spectrum of attitudes are: (i) the individual's perception of the level of danger facing the environment, (ii) the degree of reliance on the landholding as a source of income, (iii) beliefs about land use capacities of various parts of the environment, and (iv) attitudes to forestry as an appropriate use of productive private land.

The cultural understanding of farm forestry as a legitimate activity for the 'poorer' areas in the landscape in the 'traditional' and related groups is in direct conflict with newly created regulations governing forestry activities. Many landholders believe that the types of land which are not legally appropriate for forestry (e.g. steep land) are capable of sustaining forestry activities and are the only areas of their land which they wish to use for forestry. To these landholders the differences between the regulations and their own understanding translates into the feeling that their ideas and understanding of the land and its capacity is not respected, and indeed, under attack. They are sceptical of guarantees of harvest security.

While some landholders were interested in establishing plantations for pulp production, primarily because of the potential for faster financial returns, the great majority of landholders appeared to be interested in growing plantations for saw log production and other high-value uses. There is resistance to the development of timber plantations among the traditionally-orientated landholders in the sense that many are not happy with the idea that grazing land is being planted for timber production. This is, to them, a loss or at least a devaluation of a community resource. The concept that farm forestry is for 'tree people' and government agencies and not 'real farmers' needs examination. These landholders appear to be unconvinced about the need for reasonably productive land to be used for forestry in order to ensure reasonable growth rates and generate adequate financial returns.

Land management rights

The view that landholders know best how to manage their own land and that governments are unfairly restricting their right to pursue their own strategies is an example of a cultural constraint to the development of farm forestry in the region. The belief system of the 'traditional' landholders is based on the notion of 'free enterprise' and a strong sense of independence. Many landholders are proud of their self-reliance, feel that they are environmentally responsible, and strongly object to regulation of, and interference in, their land management activities by governments.

The government role

A number of issues relate to sovereign risks associated with land management. These include: the potential for changes in legislation or regulations governing land management activities; and for changes in taxation to dramatically alter the viability of land uses. Fears about the instability of land management laws or the policy environment are partly the result of major changes in the international and national framework of agreements and laws associated with the protection of the environment and partly due to the changing social characteristics of the rural community.

The relatively recent rise of radical politics in regional areas and less-advantaged parts of large urban centres indicates the extent of dissatisfaction with mainstream political parties felt by some sections of the community in these areas. Some political and social researchers and commentators have indicated that they believe this rise to be in some ways an anti-intellectual or anti-elitist movement. There are undoubtedly substantial numbers of people in the rural community who feel disenfranchised. This feeling appears to be prevalent among the 'middle-of-the-road' group as well as the 'traditional' group. They feel that the government does not pay any attention to them when setting the political agenda or making political reforms or policies. The farm lobby no longer has the political clout it once had when agricultural produce dominated Australia's exports and the whole nation 'rode on the sheeps back'. The financial returns from grazing and other extensive farming activities have been very poor or even negative for most of the last ten years because of a combination of low commodity prices and droughts. The combined effect of economically hard times, changing social values, and increased government regulation of private land management activities all contribute to calls for a stable and supportive policy environment in which landholders can make long-term decisions.

Rate of return

Despite the enthusiasm of many landholders for tree growing, the time taken for returns is a major issue. This is where joint venture schemes, particularly those with annual or six-monthly payments, can offer some relief. But problems arise because of the 'industrial' forestry approaches that are being offered to landholders. This approach includes the use of trees not endemic to the region or area, the concentration on species suitable for pulp, the concentration on planting in blocks, and the rigidity and lack of amenity value from 'industrial' plantations. Those offering joint venture plantings will have to convince landholders that tree growing, like other rural enterprises, needs good quality land to be commercially successful. The alternative would be to cut back on the inputs or equity in the arrangement offered by the 'outside' party, putting greater responsibility on the landholders to accept that growing trees in places that suit their other activities will compromise the financial viability of the enterprise. This approach would lead landholders to have a better image of those promoting timber plantations in the rural community. While it would increase the time taken to produce timber, it is likely that much greater areas could be planted. It is also likely that if this type of assistance was offered and landholders began to take a more active role in managing areas of their land for timber production, the development of a farm forestry culture

in the region, and the commitment of better quality lands to timber production in the future, would occur.

Information sources

In the interviews, a number of landholders mentioned local nursery operators, millers and furniture makers as sources of information about farm forestry. Organisations such as the Sub-Tropical Farm Forestry Association and the Upper Clarence Farm Forestry Network were also mentioned as potential sources of information about farm forestry by a number of landholders in that area. A significant proportion of landholders do have regular contact with persons involved in the forestry industry and seek advice from them. It is important for those promoting farm forestry to understand the nature of the advice which landholders are receiving. Is it at odds with that being offered by government agencies and private companies?

Role of group membership

Landholders in social networks associated with the 'lifestyler' groups are not as concerned about the policy environment in regards to the establishment of trees on their land as members of other groups. While these landholders are fundamentally interested in growing trees for conservation and personal reasons, many expressed some desire to harvest timber from their plantings as well. The main support they want to take up or expand their farm forestry activities is the provision of quality information about tree establishment and management techniques. Once they have this information, and are confident about their tree management skills, some financial assistance would be beneficial.

5.2 The relevance of group classification using innovation adoption theory

The five groups of landholders identified according to their reasons for planting trees were statistically derived from the questionnaires, and these groupings appear to be supported by the interviews. In the same way that the whole rural population should not be assumed to be homogeneous, neither should each group be seen as homogeneous. Within each group will be 'innovators' and 'traditionalists', who will be more or less ready to adopt change within the general norms of the group (Spence 1994).

Naming the groups identified according to the classifications proposed by Howden *et al.* (1998) was intended to lend some insight into the processes occurring in the community in the Northern Rivers region. The groups defined in this study, however, do not match exactly the six main groups defined by Howden *et al.* (1998). This is not unexpected, given the sociological and environmental differences between the regions studied, and the different methodologies used. Nevertheless, the interviews support the classification well, with each group representing a different position along the innovation adoption curve (Figure 3). The difference between the 'innovators' and the 'progressives', although statistically sound, is the most difficult to determine qualitatively (Tables 3 and 4). Rogers (1995) joined these two groups and called them 'early adopters', which emphasised their similarities and the differences between them and the other groups. The innovators and progressives are, as expected, the greatest risk takers, while the traditionalists are slower to adopt new ideas. The constraints perceived by each of the groups are equally variable as one moves along the innovation adoption continuum.

The positioning of the members of the community along the innovation adoption continuum illustrates that the penetration of farm forestry in the community is consistent with the theoretical model. The process of the adoption of farm forestry as a legitimate land use practice in the region should therefore follow the general pattern of innovation adoption illustrated in Figure 3. The difficulty is keeping the flow of adoption moving along the curve to a point where the innovation will become self-driven. This 'critical mass' is thought to be between 15 and 25 percent of the total population (Rogers 1995). Less than 10 percent of

landholders in the Northern Rivers region had planted trees for timber in the three years prior to 1995 (Wilson and Yannick 1995). The percentage of the respondents to the questionnaire in the present study who said they had actually planted trees for timber was 25%. If we assume the respondents to be biased towards farm forestry, having picked up and spent the time to fill in the survey, the percentage of the total landholder population may be somewhat less than 25%. Nevertheless, this figure indicates an encouraging increase in participation in tree planting in the region since 1995. Caution must be placed on the interpretation of such figures as the majority of planting (52% of those who reported planting for timber) was done by the 'early adopters' group (the innovators and progressives), and for the impetus to continue, the 'middle-of-the-road' and 'traditionals' need increasingly to participate. Further, this result was based on self-assessment by the respondents of their planting activities, and there is no consideration of the number of trees, the species planted, their management, or their success as a product.

5.3 The importance of perceptions about farm forestry across the region

The placement of members of the community along the innovation adoption spectrum is only one way in which the community can be viewed. It is useful to describe the nature and range of opinions about farm forestry in the context of sub-cultures in the rural community. This continuum ranges from philosophies that may be described as the 'alternative' or 'environmentalist' position, to the 'traditional' or 'production-oriented' position. A summary of some of the attitudes and socio-economic factors characterising these extreme positions is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Perceptions and associated socio-economic features characterising extreme positions of landholders' attitudes to farm forestry and land management objectives.

Characteristic	'Alternative'	'Traditional'
Perception of legitimate private timber production	Supports mixed species plantings of native species with high conservation values and sustainable management over long term. Revegetation more important than financial returns.	Supports environmentally sensible management of native forests for timber and the establishment of plantations on less productive land. Financial viability and short-term returns important.
Perceptions of restrictions to timber production	Lack of finance and time to establish and manage trees, lack of information about methods.	Concern over 'sovereign risks' and government regulation of forestry practices. Need to maintain sufficient area of land to keep farm viable and management options flexible.
Perceptions of public assistance	Welcomes public/outside agency support and involvement. Desire greater information about trees generally and about organic methods for tree establishment.	Independence paramount-suspicious of dealings with outside agencies, desire removal of structural impediments and a secure policy environment.
Information sources used	'Alternative' magazines, conservation groups, social circle	Dept. Ag., producers associations, social circle
Main reasons for planting	Biodiversity conservation, beautification, environmental protection, small orchards/bushfood	Support of production, beautification/land value improvement
Main species planted	Rainforest spp., eucalypt spp.	Eucalypt spp., some exotics
Main remnant vegetation type	Camphor laurel/rainforest regrowth	Eucalypt regrowth
Location of landholding	Coastal/near urban centres	Inland/remote from urban centres
Land use type	Rural residential/orchards	Grazing
Size of landholding	Small (<20 ha)	Medium/large (100-5000 ha)
Land quality/climate	Fertile soils/high rainfall, moderate temperature range	Infertile soils/low rainfall, extreme temperature range
Time owned land/succession	Relatively short/ex-metropolitan	Relatively long/inherited
Income sources and education levels	High % off-farm income, secondary-tertiary education levels	Lower % off-farm income, primary-secondary education level

The continuing evolution of land management regulations due to 'first order' events, and the cumulative effect of 'second order' events, has polarised opinions about forestry and farm forestry in the region. Most landholders hold opinions somewhere between the two extremes. It would appear that the extreme positions are descriptive of the subjective norms of the landholders in most cases. Following the theory of reasoned action (Ajzen and Fishbein 1980), the extent to which these beliefs influence a person's behaviour depends upon their confidence in their own judgements based on experience, and the circumstances in which they live. For substantial portions of the rural community the notion of good farming practice appears to be referenced to the archetypal 'alternative' or the 'traditional' positions. There still remain, however, many landholders who appear to have quite independent views about land management and the appropriate role of farm forestry. As described by Phillips and Gray (1995), landholders seek to gain social and cultural capital by following accepted farming practices possibly even more than they seek to increase their economic capital.

The five groups formed in the cluster analysis and named according to innovation adoption theory, may be placed along the cultural attitudes continuum. The 'traditionalists' in both groups are the same, and form one extreme of attitudes, but those holding the 'alternative' cultural viewpoint are best correlated to the 'lifestylers' of the innovation adoption groups and fall at the other extreme of attitudes (Figure 4). The other groups fall between the two extremes, with the 'middle-of-the-road' group lying closest in cultural attitudes to the traditionalists, the 'innovators' and 'progressives' roughly in the middle. The utility of this approach is in demonstrating the degree of adoption of a new idea by the various members of the community. The groups which have adopted farm forestry first tend to hold no extreme opinions, and thus have less to lose culturally by trying a new idea. The traditionalists, however, have more attitudinal (and possibly other) limitations than most groups and were thus placed at the end of the innovation adoption spectrum. The 'alternatives' or 'lifestylers' were the most strongly opinionated and voluble about the type of farm forestry they would engage in, and partly because of this had not joined the 'innovators' and the 'progressives' in whole-heartedly adopting farm forestry as an acceptable land use.

Figure 4: A diagrammatic depiction of the cultural spectrum of landholders' attitudes to farm forestry and the relationship of innovation adoption groups. Group numbers according to the cluster analysis are shown.

It is incorrect to say that an individual's attitude to farm forestry or the cultural belief system to which they subscribe, are the sole factors limiting their participation in farm forestry. Analysis of the differences in responses to the questionnaire between those who are presently involved in farm forestry and those who are not, clearly indicates that the time taken for financial returns is a major impediment to the adoption of farm forestry. These findings were supported by the telephone survey, with many of the interviewees indicating that financial factors were the critical restriction to their involvement. The stabilisation of the policy environment in conjunction with schemes to provide faster financial returns from farm forestry could lead to substantial increases in the adoption of farm forestry in the region by those landholders whose beliefs are more or less traditional.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The project has revealed a considerable diversity in landholders' perceptions of farm forestry in the Northern Rivers region of New South Wales. Different sectors or groups within the rural community have different perspectives about farming and forestry and ways in which these activities can or should be combined. These groups may or may not be spatially related. These differences are related to:

- (i) the sociological backgrounds of the landholders and their related personality traits and communication behaviour;
- (ii) the biophysical environment of their landholding, including the effects of previous management on the landholding; and
- (iii) the types of land uses practised and the dependence of landholders on their land for regular income.

The above factors combine to produce the different perceptions of landholders. Although it is clear that each landholder needs to be regarded as an individual when carrying out extension, the consideration of the rural community as an assembly of unrelated individuals or as a homogenous group does little to aid the development of policies to promote farm forestry. In this report are described a number of groups within the community, and these can be used to design and target farm forestry development programs. While these groups do not appear to be mutually exclusive or even exhaustive, they represent one of the first attempts to apply this type of methodology to the issues of rural development and some useful strategies can be developed from the results of the project.

The constraints applying to each group can be differentiated using Ecologically Sustainable Development criteria as social, environmental and economic (Australia 1990 and 1992). These constraints are a product of the position of the members of the group along the innovation adoption continuum, their cultural position, and the physical environment in which they are working (Table 6). These constraints can provide a starting point for the development of assistance and incentive schemes. Each group, in addition, has a different type of preferred product from their timber, which is also the result of several contributing factors, including the knowledge and acceptance of farm forestry as a legitimate land use option by the members of the group. The combination of the constraints, actual and perceived, by each group, and their preferred timber product, allows appropriate actions to be proposed. These actions are listed in Table 6, and range from the support of existing activities to the publication of regulations concerning farm forestry activities. The nature of the recommended action changes with group characteristics, and as the group moves 'up' the innovation adoption continuum. When farm forestry is still a foreign idea, suggested activities are the publication of regulations, and the promotion or initiation of ventures which alter current farming practices as little as possible. As the landholder becomes more committed, the assistance required becomes more specific to timber as a product. These requirements will no doubt change further over time as the landholders become more experienced and further advanced in their production cycle.

Knowledge of the position of each group along the innovation adoption continuum (Figure 3) and its position along the cultural attitude continuum (Figure 4) allows these actions to be prioritised. The proposed actions listed in Table 6 are prioritised from A (most important) to C. It is crucial to ensure that good and successful demonstrations are available, as many new land management practices are best 'sold' by concrete example, rather than by theoretical persuasion. Support of existing activities by the innovators and the progressives is the quickest way to ensure such demonstrations are available. Care must be taken not to alienate other groups, however, and only providing support for those already committed will not speed

the adoption of farm forestry. Thus it is proposed that high priority be given to appropriate attention to the 'middle-of-the-road' group. This group is a group which is sceptical and cautious in adopting new ideas, but less opinionated than the 'traditionalists'. The 'middle-of-the-roaders' are not a group that is seen as 'alternative' or, indeed 'innovative', and actions by this group will be observed with interest by the 'traditionalists' and thus should bring the slowest innovators into farm forestry more quickly. A series of workshops and field days about various topics, regular input to land management group meetings, as well as regular dissemination of legislative and regulatory conditions, would be appropriate ways to engage in extension. It is most important to ensure that accurate information is regularly publicised about legislative decisions, in order to decrease the spread of misinformation among all segments of the timber industry. The effect of dissatisfaction and concerns by other components of the industry filters very quickly in these small, often tight-knit communities, and will increase the uncertainty of the landholder in perceiving forestry as a legitimate activity for their farm. It is very important, especially for the later adopters, that forestry is seen as a complementary and beneficial activity for their properties and to work sensitively with the landholder.

Although large sections of the rural community in the Northern Rivers region have little or no experience with farm forestry, there are still a significant number of landholders with an intimate understanding of farm forestry gained through decades of experience. These people could form the basis for the development of a farm forestry culture in the community. They could perhaps help to teach other landholders about silviculture and help to resolve misunderstandings about the legal and financial implications of farm forestry. It is important that a number of non-government organisations as well as government agencies able to advise landholders about farm forestry are maintained and encouraged. It is vital that a sense of community ownership of farm forestry as an activity and industry in the region is developed.

Table 6: Constraints to farm forestry development perceived by different groups in the rural community and actions to address these constraints. Group names are in accordance with innovation adoption theory (Tables 2 and 4), with the exception of the 'lifestyler' perspective (section 4.3) which is subdivided to emphasise the gradient of opinions and problems that exists within all groups.

Group	Social constraints	Environmental constraints	Economic constraints	Preferred products	Actions	Priority
Innovators	Lack of technical/ silvicultural information	Matching species to sites; selection of best planting material.	Time and capital for establishment; lack of markets.	All/any timber and non-wood products	Support existing activities; provide more silvicultural advice; organise marketing	A
Progressive	Lack of technical/ silvicultural information; integrating forestry with grazing	Matching species with sites; selection of best planting material.	Time and capital for establishment; loss of grazing land; lack of markets	Saw logs, veneer logs	Support existing activities; provide more silvicultural advice; organise marketing	A
Lifestylers	Lack of information about 'organic' methods, and about cabinet timber and mixed species plantation silviculture	Weed (camphor laurel) control; maximising conservation benefits	Time and capital for establishment; lack of specialised equipment	Cabinet timbers and non-wood products	Provide data from silviculture experiments; potential for planting assistance	B
Lifestylers - hobby farmers	General lack of information about available supports; age limits interest in timber production;	Weed control	Lack of space; lack specialised equipment and capital	Saw logs, veneer logs	Potential for joint ventures/ planting assistance	C
Lifestylers - traditional	Distrust of public agencies and environmental movement; view forestry as not suitable for quality private lands	Low productivity soils	not clear	Saw logs, veneer logs	Publicise existing regulations and harvest security	C
Middle of the road	Distrust of public agencies and environmental movement; view forestry as not suitable for quality private lands	not clear	Low equity/high dependence on landholding for income; perceived loss of flexibility	Saw logs, pulp wood	Publicise existing regulations; tailor joint ventures to support agricultural and conservation benefits.	A
Traditional	Distrust of public agencies and environmental movement; view forestry as not suitable for quality private lands	Low productivity soils common; <i>Eucalyptus</i> regrowth management	Low equity/high dependence on landholding for income; perceived loss of flexibility	Saw logs, pulp wood	Publicise existing regulations and harvest security; provide information about native vegetation management	C

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